

Study of Corn Production in Mexico and Its Trade Regulations through NAFTA-USMCA

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Abstract

The main of this paper is to evaluate the productive and commercial dynamics of Mexican corn in the period 1980-2022. The methodological approach focuses on ordinary least squares and dynamic panel data models. The research contribution includes an analysis of commercial regulations and the productive performance of corn over a broad time horizon. It is established that as a result of the implementation of NAFTA and its move to the USMCA that as a result of the liberalization of the corn market, production and yield levels have increased. However, there is a very marked duality in grain production since the entities of the northwest and the shoal register much higher yields than those located in the south and center of the country, which reaffirms the heterogeneity that occurs not only in the cultivation of corn but in the Mexican countryside in general.

Keywords: Corn, trade regulation, production, performance, NAFTA.

Introduction

Corn is one of the most important crops in the Mexican market because it is crucial for the food security of people in both rural and urban areas. It is also one of the country's most important agricultural products because it promotes the creation of jobs and generates income for a sector of the population. According to the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Environmental Resources, SAGARPA (2022), corn producers make up 43% of the agricultural labor force and constitute 20% of production in the primary sector in 2022. These figures corroborate the importance of corn cultivation in the national economy.

Following the ratification of the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), a large body of literature has been written on its economic and commercial effects on the agricultural sector. Massieu and Lechuga (2002) analyze changes in corn consumption and production since the implementation of the treaty; Steffen and Echánove (2007) analyze the effects of grain marketing programs on production; while (Moreno-Sáenz et al., 2016) analyze the degree of dependence of the agricultural sector on imports during the treaty era and (Cruz et al., 2017) evaluate the behavior of the agricultural sector before and after the trade agreement.

The objective of this article is to explain the dynamics of Mexican corn production and trade in the context of the trade regulations that arose before NAFTA and later with the USMCA (United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement); and in an economic context, through the yield obtained from corn production at the national and state levels. The proposed methodology employs the ordinary least squares model to estimate the performance of corn production based on both internal and external variables, and the panel data model is applied to measure the yield behavior of corn production.

The work is organized in five sections, in addition to this introduction. First, we examine the trade regulations that existed during NAFTA and their modifications under the USMCA. Second, we present the methods applied in the research, with the two econometric techniques: ordinary least squares and panel data. Third, this involves descriptive statistics through the evolution of production. Fourth, we present the results and discussion of the econometric estimates. And fifth, the conclusions.

Trade regulations in the corn market

Since Mexico joined NAFTA, it has become the third largest market for U.S. agricultural products. Trade liberalization led to a process of tariff relief for several different products, such as corn and beans, where agricultural and agro-industrial chains were considered. These products had competitiveness problems in Mexico due to the conditions that were agreed upon, which included customs tariffs, quantitative restrictions, technical and agricultural marketing standards, and the restriction of subsidies, among other benefits. Below are the corn market regulations that existed prior to NAFTA, as well as whether there have been changes with the implementation of the USMCA.

Trade regulations in the corn market

With the implementation of NAFTA, trade between Mexico and the United States has increased exponentially. According to the National Institute of Statistics, Geography and Informatics (INEGI), from January to March 2023, exports of non-oil goods to the United States grew by 5.2%. The value of agricultural and fishing exports in August was US\$1,388 million (INEGI, 2023). There is currently no political dispute between the countries that are parties to this treaty that could jeopardize trade relations; on the contrary, in commercial terms, the trilateral relationship is growing stronger day by day.

Non-tariff barriers in NAFTA

In Mexico, a gradual phase-out process was implemented for a limited set of products, including corn, beans, powdered milk, chicken, barley and potatoes, and where agricultural and agro-industrial chains were considered, since Mexican producers faced serious difficulties in terms of competitiveness (Hernández, 2021). According to Chapter VII of the decree enacting NAFTA, published on December 20, 1993, which corresponds to the agricultural sector, sanitary and phytosanitary measures, Article 703 establishes that the parties will work to improve access to their respective markets by reducing or eliminating import barriers to trade in agricultural products, including tariffs, quantitative restrictions, technology and trade standards for agricultural products. (DOF, 1993).

With respect to Article 705 subsidies, the common objective of both parties is to achieve multilateral cancellation of agricultural export subsidies. Therefore, they concluded that it is not useful for one party to subsidize the export of a specific agricultural product to the territory of the other party, especially if there are no other import subsidies for the product in the territory of the other party. However, there are significant differences in production levels among the signatory countries, exacerbated by U.S. protectionist policies towards farmers. These policies provide them with incentives and financial support, providing support for crop insurance and implementing agricultural export promotion programs. This situation gives the U.S. agricultural industry an advantage over the Mexican agricultural industry, resulting in a large difference in food prices, with Mexico being the big loser. (Senate of the Republic, 2008).

According to the Mexican Senate (2008), in 2001 the United States was the only one of the three NAFTA countries to increase aid above pre-signing and pre-ratification levels, unfairly putting the other countries at a disadvantage. Under the original treaty, only non-discriminatory aid could be implemented, which the United States clearly did not do. The sanitary and phytosanitary measures defined in Article 712 of the same decree constitute another important provision on non-tariff barriers, establishing the right for each party to take, maintain or implement all necessary measures to protect human, animal or plant life or health in its territory (DOF, 1993).

Tariff barriers in NAFTA

Under NAFTA Chapter 7, Mexico successfully negotiated the introduction of tariff quotas for certain sensitive agricultural products, such as corn and beans. A duty-free import system was established until certain quotas were reached. As soon as this quota is exceeded, significant tariffs are imposed, which are to be progressively reduced over a period of 15 years until they are completely eliminated. That is, NAFTA provides for a general reduction in grain tariffs for 10 to 15 years with the following objectives: Tariff quotas are established for corn and beans. Table 1 shows the NAFTA program to reduce corn tariffs in the form of ad valorem tariffs.

Table 1. NAFTA tariff elimination program for Ad valorem corn tariff

Year	Originating in the United States	Originating in Canada
Base rate	215.0	215.0
1994	206.4	206.4
1995	197.8	197.8
1996	189.2	189.2
1997	180.6	180.6
1998	172.0	172.0
1999	163.4	163.4
2000	145.2	145.2
2001	127.1	127.1
2002	108.9	108.9
2003	90.8	90.8
2004	72.6	72.6
2005	54.5	54.5
2006	36.3	36.3
2007	18.2	18.2
2008	0	0

Source: Center for the Study of Public Finances CEFP of the House of Representatives. (2000).

An ad valorem quota tariff of 215% was set for white or yellow corn, which was reduced in 15 steps from 1994 to 2008, when the negotiated minimum quota for corn was completely abolished: 10.34% for white corn and 89.66% for yellow corn (Senate of the Republic, 2008). The drought that affected the Mexican countryside in 1996 caused a significant drop in corn production. This led to a significant increase in corn imports, far in excess of the quantities agreed to in NAFTA. Although weather conditions were considered normal the following year, unfavorable conditions returned in 1998, causing corn imports to exceed NAFTA quotas once again. This trend continued in 1999 and 2000, making the Mexican countryside less competitive in food production (House of Representatives, 2000).

In the first six years of NAFTA, Mexico exceeded U.S. corn import quotas five times without paying additional quota import tariffs under the agreement, which meant that Mexico expanded corn import quotas by more than \$1.5 billion. Table 2 shows the NAFTA quotas applicable to corn imports originating in the United States for the period 1994-2000.

Table 2. Mexico: Quota applicable under NAFTA to imports of corn originating in the United States 1994-2000 tariff item (1005.90.99)

Year	Total imported		Quota	Over quota		Over quota tariff		Tariff not collected due to over quota	
	Value (million dollars)	Volume (metric tons)	Volume (metric tons)	Value (million dollars)	Volume (metric tons)	Ad-valorem tariff	Base rate	With ad-valorem tariff	With base rate
1994	369,339	2,745,897	2,500,000	33,073	245,897	206.4	0.197	68,263	48,442
1995	375.782	2,686,743	2,575,000	15.629	111,743	197.8	0.189	30,914	21,119
1996	796.351	5,693.702	2,652,250	425.393	3,041,452	189.2	0.181	804,844	550,503
1997	321,757	2,488,539	2,731,818	n.a	n.a.	180.6	0.173	n.a	n.a.
1998	602,166	5,305,392	2,813,773	282,801	2,491,619	172.0	0.164	486,418	408,626
1999	580,081	5,494,936	2,898,186	274,130	2,596,750	163.4	0.156	447,928	405,093
2000	576,180	5,380,534	2,985,132	256,514	2,395,402	145.2	0.139	372,458	332,961
Total	2,081,725	18,680,527	16,171,027	1,287.540	10,882,863			2,210,825	1,766,743

Source: Center for the Study of Public Finances of the House of Representatives. (2000).

Non-tariff barriers in the USMCA

On October 3, 2022, President Andrés Manuel López Obrador led the signing of the Opening Agreement against Inflation and Scarcity (Apecic) between the Government of Mexico, producers, distributors and food companies to help counteract the rising cost of agricultural products and reduce regulatory and logistical costs. In the framework of mutual trust, the federal government granted a joint license to the signatory companies. This license exempts the aforementioned company from all procedures or licenses, including those required by the National Service for Agri-Food Health, Safety and Quality (Senasica) and the Federal Committee for Protection against Sanitary Risk (Cofepris). The government will focus more on plans to strengthen the country's grain deficit production and cancel white corn exports as part of the agreement. (AMLO, 2022) In this way, food producers, distributors and companies are responsible for ensuring that the products they market meet quality and sanitary safety standards.

Tariff Barriers in the USMCA

Table 3 below shows the tariff rates applicable to corn by Mexico, the United States and Canada as of the entry into force of the USMCA.

Table 3. Tariffs under the USMCA corn tariffs

United States			
Tariff item	Description	Tariff for Canada	Tariff for Mexico
1005.10.00	<i>Seed corn (maize)</i>	0	0
Mexico			
		Tariff for USA	Tariff for Canada
1005.90.04	White corn (flour)	0	0
Canada			
		Tariff for Mexico	Tariff for USA
1005.10.00	<i>Seed</i>	0	0

Source: Own elaboration with data from the tariff schedule of the United States, tariff schedule of Mexico (2023) and tariff schedule of Canada. (2024).

Pursuant to Article 2 of the aforementioned decree, tariffs have been temporarily adjusted to the tariff rates of the General Import and Export Tax Law. The tariffs were published in the Official Gazette of the Federation (DOF) on June 7, 2022, and were subsequently adjusted. Table 4 describes the expected changes that will become effective the day after the publication of the DOF and will be in effect until December 31, 2023.

Table 4. Modification of legal regulations related to white corn tariffs.

Code:	Description	Unit	Quota (tariff)	
			IMP	EXP
1005	Corn			
1005.90.04	White corn flour	Kg	50	50

Source: Own elaboration with data from the DOF (2023).

According to the Government of Mexico, Chapter 2, Article 2.4 of the USMCA (2023), paragraph 1 states "Except as otherwise provided in this Agreement, no Party shall increase any existing customs duty, or adopt any new customs duty, on an originating good" (p.4). Article 2.15 of the same Chapter 2 states that "No Party shall adopt or maintain any tariff, tax or other charge on the export of any good to the territory of another Party, unless such tariff, tax or charge is also applied to that good when destined for domestic consumption" (p. 20). Therefore, it is appropriate to continue with the tariff extensions agreed upon at the outset. It is understood that tariffs do not apply to U.S. corn due to existing free market commitments under the USMCA.

Methodological aspects

Ordinary least squares (OLS)

This method seeks to minimize the variation between observations by estimating the coefficients of the model with the lowest possible errors, also called residuals. According to Hanke and Wichern (2006) this technique is based on minimizing the sum of the squared residuals, i.e., OLS reduces the differences between the data analyzed. On the other hand, (Anderson et al. 2015) indicate that the adjustment procedure establishes an efficient relationship between the explained variable and the explanatory variables.

The variables in the model are: Mexican corn production, Mexican inflation rate, U.S. inflation rate, peso/dollar exchange rate, Mexican corn exports, Mexican corn imports and the price of Mexican corn on the Chicago Stock Exchange. A growth rate is obtained for each variable to standardize the estimation criteria. Inflation indicators use the consumer price indexes for Mexico and the United States from INEGI and the International Monetary Fund (IMF), respectively. Exchange rates were obtained from the Bank of Mexico. Levels of corn production, export and import are from the Agricultural, Food and Fisheries Information Service (SIAP). Finally, corn prices on the Chicago Stock Exchange are derived from historical investing data.

The objective is to use OLS methods to determine the extent to which these variables influence the productive behavior of Mexican corn, as shown in the following equation:

$$gy_t = \alpha + \beta g\delta_{i,t} + \beta g\varphi_{i,t} + \beta g\tau_{i,t} + \beta g\xi_{i,t} + g\partial_{i,t} + \beta g\sigma_{i,t} + u_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

Where gy_t is the average growth rate of corn production in Mexico while the $g\delta_{i,t}$ variable represents the increase in Mexico's price level; $g\varphi_{i,t}$ is the change in the U.S. inflation rate; $g\tau_{i,t}$ is the change in the peso/dollar exchange rate; $g\xi_{i,t}$ is the growth rate of Mexico's corn exports; $g\partial_{i,t}$ represents the increase in Mexico's corn imports, and; $g\sigma_{i,t}$ is the percentage change in corn prices on the Chicago Stock Exchange.

With regard to the time horizon of the study, two periods are analyzed: 1981-1994 and 1994-2022. The first covers the period prior to NAFTA, when the priority of the Mexican economy was the domestic market. Whereas the second period contemplates an analysis of the behavior of corn production post-NAFTA. The purpose is to determine whether there are differences in the variables before the implementation of the trade agreement and after their incorporation into the agreement. A total of 104 observations were used in the first period and 224 observations in the second period, for a total of 328 data in the model.

Panel data models

Panel models allow us to distinguish correlations between individual effects that may be associated with model variables. According to Sancho and Serrano (2005), panel data are derived from cross-sectional or transverse observations of a data set over time, while the former analyzes individual units observed over time. On the other hand, the latter examines

variables at a specific time and therefore does not involve time. Thus, panel data methods capture the space used for a set of study variables at each point in time.

Meanwhile, De la Rosa (2016) indicates that the panel data methodology makes possible a greater quantity of information, less collinearity between variables, greater variability and better precision of the results. According to Baronio and Vianco (2014) panel data incorporate the study of economic agents--individuals, companies, regions, countries--in a given period of time, thus combining structural and temporal dimensions. With this, the panel data tool performs a more dynamic study by introducing the time dimension of the data, which in periods of significant change broadens and improves the analysis.

In this sense, the variables of the second model refer to the local corn market, namely: corn production value, area planted with corn, area of corn harvested, corn price level and corn yield per hectare. For the comparison of the variables, average annual growth rates were obtained in order to establish the impact of each variable on the increase in national corn production. The panel data modeling technique is used through the following equation:

$$gy_t = \alpha + \beta g\theta_{i,t} + \beta g\mu_{i,t} + \beta g\rho_{i,t} + \beta g\omega_{i,t} + u_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

In which gy_t is the explained variable, it refers to the average annual growth rate of corn production; $g\theta_{i,t}$ shows the percentage change in the area planted with corn; $g\mu_{i,t}$ indicates the annual increase in the area of corn harvested; $\rho_{i,t}$ represents the increase in the price level of corn, and $g\omega_{i,t}$ constitutes the growth rate of corn yield. This panel model includes the 32 Mexican states for the period 1981-2022, so a total of 6,560 observations are considered.

Evolution of corn production in Mexico

Figure 1 shows the yield levels of corn production in Mexico from 1980 to 2022. It can be observed that in the 80's there was a very flat performance and even a slight decrease in yield in the last years of the decade, obtaining an average of 1.76 tons per hectare. By the 1990s, since NAFTA came into effect, yields increased significantly, so the average yield for that decade was 2.26 tons per year. In terms of the 2000s, there has been continuous growth with an average of 2.90 per hectare.

During the 2010s there were increases and decreases in yields, although at the end of the decade the trend resumed with significant growth, reaching an average yield of 3.47 tons per hectare. In 2022, the last year available when this article was written, a yield of 3.90 tons per hectare was reached. The data in the graph reflect the continuous growth in corn production yields in Mexico from 1.80 to 3.90 tons per hectare, an increase of 216%, which is indicative of the improvements generated in productivity per hectare.

Graph 1. Yield levels of corn production in Mexico: 1980-2022.

Source: Own elaboration with data from the SIAP (2023).

Table 5 shows a comparison of production and yields of the main corn producing states in Mexico for 1980 and 2022. In the initial year, the states with the highest production accounted for 64% of the national total: Jalisco contributed 18%, the State of Mexico 14%, Chiapas 10%, Tamaulipas 8%, Puebla 7% and Michoacán 6%. The remaining 26 states accounted for 36% of production. In terms of yield, there is not much difference since the main producers average 2.20 tons per hectare, while the rest of the entities average 1.60 tons, placing the national average at 1.83 tons per hectare.

Table 5. Comparative production and yield of the main corn producing states in Mexico: 1980 and 2022.

Year 1980:			Year 2022:		
State	Production	Yield	State	Production	Yield
Jalisco	2224157	2.61	Sinaloa	5309195	11.62
State of Mexico	1813280	2.68	Jalisco	3984289	7.02
Chiapas	1185080	2.35	Michoacán	2093142	4.37
Tamaulipas	1000077	2.08	Guanajuato	1898925	5.09
Puebla	966215	1.81	State of Mexico	1779468	3.85
Michoacán	764055	1.64	Chihuahua	1731211	7.98
Best states	7952864	2.20	Best states	16796230	6.66
Rest of states (26)	4421114	1.60	Rest of states (26)	9757009	3.39
National	12373978	1.83	National	26553239	3.90

Source: Own elaboration with data from the SIAP (2023).

By 2022, there are significant changes in the yield ranges in the states with the highest production, which account for 63% of production: Sinaloa contributes 20%, Jalisco 15%,

Michoacán 8%, Guanajuato 7%, State of Mexico 7%, and Chihuahua 6%. The remaining states contribute 37% of production. The trend shown in 1980 is maintained, with similar shares of the main producing states. In relation to yield, in contrast to the initial year, there is a marked difference, with Sinaloa obtaining a yield of 11.62 tons per hectare, placing the main producers at an average of 6.66, while the rest of the states have an average of 3.39 and the national average is 3.90 tons per hectare.

Econometric evaluation

Table 6 shows the estimates of equation (1). In the first period, it can be seen that the Mexican inflation rate, corn exports, corn prices on the Chicago Stock Exchange and Mexican corn production are positively related to corn prices, since an increase in these variables leads to an increase in corn prices. Meanwhile, the U.S. inflation rate, peso/dollar exchange rate and corn imports have an inverse relationship with corn prices, so an increase in these variables will cause corn prices to decrease.

Table 6. Regression of corn price growth rates with respect to the degree of influence of different variables: 1981-1994 and 1994-2022.

Explanatory variables	1981-1994	1994-2022
Constant	-0.080737	-0.037314
	(-0.38665)	(-0.64826)
Mexican inflation rate	1.078725	1.117219
	(7.59589)	(4.39847)
U.S. inflation rate	-0.672266	4.155100
	(-2.14168)	(2.19055)
Peso/dollar exchange rate	-0.025958	-3.306781
	(-1.82869)	(-2.03560)
Corn exports	0.023685	0.009429
	(1.15467)	(0.48213)
Corn imports	-0.024647	-0.015704
	(-1.05502)	(-0.55292)
Corn prices, Chicago Stock Exchange	0.187430	0.233928
	(2.13743)	(1.86533)
Corn production in Mexico	0.606552	-0.366624
	(1.91198)	(-2.12905)
Durbin-Watson	2.021868	2.032663
F test	0.006669	0.002845
R ²	0.918544	0.607355

Source: Own elaboration with data from the SIAP: 1980-2022.

It is worth noting that all independent variables are statistically significant except corn exports and imports, which is consistent since the variables are highly related. Similarly, the Durbin-Watson estimator shows that there is no autocorrelation problem among the variables; the F-test indicates that the model is significant as a function of related variables; the R² coefficient adequately and robustly predicts the model with high explanatory power.

For the second period, 1994-2022, the variables that show a positive relationship with the corn price level are the Mexican inflation rate, the U.S. inflation rate, corn exports and corn prices on the Chicago Stock Exchange, while the peso/dollar exchange rate, corn imports and the level of domestic corn production register a negative relationship with the dependent variable. On the one hand, the inflation rate in the United States is directly related to the price of corn, which could be explained by the fact that when NAFTA came into effect between the two countries, this index has a greater impact on the explained variable.

Another change that occurs between periods is that production levels have a negative coefficient; that is, an increase in production causes a decrease in the price of corn, which follows the law of supply. Judging by the test given by the model, each variable maintains the previous trend, confirming statistical significance. The Durbin-Watson and F-test estimators continue to give similar results, so the model is significant and there are no problems of autocorrelation between the variables. At the same time, the R² coefficient decreases considerably compared to the first period, although it retains significant explanatory power.

Table 7 shows the regression of the yield level of corn production with respect to the variables corn production, prices, planting, and harvest for the period 1981-2022. A dynamic panel data model is used for the 32 Mexican states. The estimators obtained show a positive relationship between the level of production and the yield per hectare, so that increasing production leads to an increase in yield. As for the price variable, an inverse relationship with the dependent variable is observed, so that as the price level increases, the yield per hectare increases.

Table 7. Regression of corn yield level: 1981-2022

Explanatory variables	Coefficient
Constant	0.050434 (5.65737)
Production	0.034346 (25.33942)
Harvested area	-0.035400 (-7.02487)
Area planted	-0.072837 (-3.61144)
Prices	-0.005317 (-0.26009)
Durbin-Watson	2.606523
F test	0.000000
R ²	0.522142

Source: Own elaboration with data from the SIAP: 1980-2022.

The coefficient of the area planted variable shows a negative sign with statistical significance, indicating that the increase in hectares planted has a negative effect on the yield level. In this sense, the parameter of the harvested area variable registers a negative

relationship, so that an increase in the corn harvest leads to a decrease in the yield per hectare. In addition, the Durbin-Watson estimator shows that there are no autocorrelation problems among the variables; the t-statistic indicates that all variables except price are statistically significant, and the model has adequate explanatory power.

In short, the evolution of Mexican corn production shows significant growth throughout the study period. That is, with the implementation of NAFTA and the corresponding liberalization of the corn market, there has been a substantial increase in production levels. Likewise, in terms of corn yields per hectare, there is a growing trend that has been consolidated with the trade agreement. However, regional differences have become more and more acute, since the northwestern and Bajío states have much higher average yields than those located in the south and center of the country, which confirms the heterogeneity that is present not only in corn cultivation but in the Mexican countryside in general.

Conclusions

The study has focused on the evolution of Mexican corn in terms of trade and production regulations in order to measure the impact of the treaty on member countries. In terms of trade regulations, it is noted that the existence of a marked difference between production and consumption levels has caused Mexican producers to have significant disadvantages due to the economic incentives and support received in the United States. Regarding non-tariff barriers, each country has established the necessary measures to protect human, animal and plant health, unless there is discrimination between goods traded between member states.

The USMCA was created to maintain Mexico's position in global production chains as a pole of attraction for foreign investment. In this regard, Mexico has fulfilled its obligation to try to compensate for higher prices of agricultural products and reduce regulatory costs. In this regard, in 2022, the Opening Agreement against Inflation and Scarcity (Apecic) was created between the Government of Mexico, producers, distributors and food companies, which are granted a license that exempts them from complying with regulations that make food imports and their mobility within the country more expensive.

Once the OLS estimations are made, the results show that corn prices are positively related to the Mexican inflation rate, the U.S. inflation rate, the prices of corn traded on the Chicago Stock Exchange and the levels of Mexican corn exports, and they are inversely related to changes in corn production levels, changes in the peso/dollar exchange rate and corn imports. For the panel data model, it is established that corn yield per hectare is strongly and positively linked to the level of production and has an inverse relationship with the area planted, area harvested and corn prices.

This article has sought to identify the productive and commercial dynamics of Mexican corn before and during the implementation of NAFTA in order to describe the effects caused by the trade agreement and the results of the transition to the USMCA. The findings indicate that although there has been significant growth in terms of corn production

and yields, it is also evident that there has been a very marked duality, concentrated in only a few states. In terms of trade regulations, corn prices are becoming increasingly volatile. It is therefore a priority to implement regional policies that promote more equitable growth of corn in the member countries of the trade agreement.

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